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Durability of Conventional vs. 3D-Printed Carbon Fiber in Harsh Saline Environments

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Overview

- Carbon fiber composites are prized for high strength-to-weight ratios but can degrade in saline environments.
- Carbon fiber composites materials for ocean applications.

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Background and Motivation

- **Marine Need:** Lightweight, strong materials for seawater exposure
- **Goals:** Prevent failure, reduce maintenance, enable design flexibility, and support sustainability.
- **Challenge:** Complex loads + Geometries → Coupled degradation behavior

Research Questions

- How do epoxy, vinyl ester, and Onyx degrade in saline conditions?
- How do water uptake and strength retention differ?
- How does microstructural damage evolve over time?
- **Goal: Predict failure onset, location, and underlying mechanisms**

Multi-scale experimental and modeling approach

Literature Review

- **Moisture ingress and salt crystallization in micro-voids** are key initiators of damage in composites exposed to saline environments.
- Studies (Shirangi et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2017) show that **crystal growth creates internal stress**, leading to **cracking, debonding, and delamination**.
- This mechanism is critical in marine applications facing **cyclic loading and humidity variations**.

MECHANISM OF SALT CRYSTALLIZATION IN A MICRO-VOID

Experiment Design

Immersion Study

Concurrent test

Hydrostatic test

Varying temperatures, stresses, and shapes

Microstructure Characterization

Micro X-ray CT

Microstructural model

To study the effect of microstructures on composite degradation

Methodology for Material Preparation and Testing

CFRP (VARTM-Hand Layup):

- **Fiber:** 3K plain weave carbon
- **Resins:** Epoxy & Derakane Vinyl Ester
- **Samples:** 20 epoxy & 20 vinyl ester (ASTM D3039 tensile)

3D-Printed Onyx (Markforged):

- 15 samples total:
- 5 tensile (ASTM D638)
- 5 bending (ASTM D790)
- 5 compression (ASTM D695)

Experiment Design: Water Uptake

- Immersion of CFRP composites in simulated saline solution at RT

Data from 20 samples each

Change in dimension < 2% for CFRP Vinyl ester and < 3% for CFRP Epoxy

Experiment Design: Water Uptake

- Immersion of CFRP (Epoxy) composites in Seawater vs. 3.5% NaCl

Data from 20 samples each

Mechanical Tests: Immersed (150 Days) vs. Dry (CFRP)

ASTM D3039 Sample	Avg. Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Avg. Tensile Strength (MPa)	Avg. Tensile Strain (%)
Dry	36.49 ± 3.62	336.95 ± 31.82	1.03 ± 0.23
Immersed	33.99 ± 4.06	311.87 ± 27.54	0.86 ± 0.11
% Drop	6.85% ↓	7.44% ↓	16.50% ↓

ASTM D3039 Sample	Avg. Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Avg. Tensile Strength (MPa)	Avg. Tensile Strain (%)
Dry	37.22 ± 2.60	367.88 ± 46.09	0.93 ± 0.02
Immersed	44.93 ± 5.38	381.92 ± 58.67	0.86 ± 0.23
% Drop	20.72% ↑	3.82% ↑	7.53% ↓

Experiment Design: Water Uptake

- Immersion of 3D Printed Onyx in simulated saline solution at RT

3.5% Saline Diffusion in 3D Printed Onyx

Data from 5 samples each

Change in dimension < 4% for Onyx

Mechanical Tests: Immersed (50 Days) vs. Dry (Onyx)

Sample ASTM D638	Avg. Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Avg. Tensile Strength (MPa)	Avg. Toughness (MPa)
Dry	0.885 ± 0.047	44.62 ± 0.66	2164.46 ± 601.04
Immersed	0.386 ± 0.004	27.76 ± 1.15	1259.64 ± 230.63
% Drop	56.38% ↓	37.79 ↓	41.81 ↓

---> Average of 3 Samples

---> Average of 5 Samples

ASTM D638 Onyx after tensile test

Mechanical Tests: Immersed (50 Days) vs. Dry (Onyx)

Sample ASTM D695	Compressive Modulus (GPa)	Stress at $\epsilon=20\%$ (MPa)	Toughness (MPa)
Dry	1.075 ± 0.267	72.46 ± 8.27	18288.27 ± 240.59
Immersed	0.351 ± 0.003	27.11 ± 0.18	6266.69 ± 190.04
% Drop	67.35% ↓	62.58% ↓	65.74% ↓

--- Average of 3 Samples

--- Average of 5 Samples

Mechanical Tests: Immersed (50 Days) vs. Dry (Onyx)

Sample ASTM D790	Bending Modulus (GPa)	Bending Strength (MPa)
Dry	0.67 ± 0.192	28.98 ± 2.80
Immersed	0.412 ± 0.008	19.96 ± 0.05
% Drop	38.51% ↓	31.13% ↓

---> Average of 3 Samples

---> Average of 5 Samples

ASTM D790 Onyx after bending test

Microstructural Characterization: Surface Profilometry (ONYX)

Rectilinear (Linear) Infill

Concentric (Circular) Infill

Microstructural Characterization: SEM (Onyx)

Dry

**Immersed
 4 months
 3.5% NaCl**

Microstructural Characterization: SEM CFRP (Epoxy)

Dry

Immersed
 4 months
 3.5% NaCl

Immersed
 4 months
 3.5% NaCl

Microstructural Characterization: SEM CFRP (Vinyl Ester)

Dry

Immersed
 4 months
 3.5% NaCl

Microstructural Characterization: Micro-CT X-ray (Onyx)

Microstructural Characterization: Micro-CT X-ray (CFRP)

Vinyl Ester

Dry

Immersed

11.883 μm resolution

Dry

Immersed
 3.5% NaCl
 5 months

Dry

Immersed

11.883 μm resolution

Epoxy

Dry

Immersed
 3.5% NaCl
 5 months

1.3 – 1.7 mm

Diffusion Responses of Onyx Compression Specimens

Fick's second law

$$\frac{\partial C_f}{\partial t} = D_f \nabla^2 C_f$$

Diffusion Responses of Onyx Tensile Specimens

Diffusion Responses of Onyx Bending Specimens

Fick's second law

$$\frac{\partial C_f}{\partial t} = D_f \nabla^2 C_f$$

Day 1

Day 2

Day 3

Diffusion Responses of CFRP (Epoxy) Specimens

C_f vs Time | Day 1/130 Mean=0.422 Max=1.000 Med=0.130 Std=0.453

Diffusion Responses of CFRP (Epoxy) Specimens

- **Fickian Diffusion Model (1D Slab Geometry):**

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = 1 - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{8}{(2n+1)^2 \pi^2} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 Dt}{4L^2}\right)$$

- M_t : Moisture content at time t
- M_∞ : Saturation moisture content (% weight gain)
- D: Diffusion coefficient (m^2/s)
- L: Half thickness of the sample (m) – Used average dry thickness
- t: Time (s).

Interpretation:

This is a **classic model for diffusion** through a flat slab. It assumes:

- Uniform material,
- Constant D,
- No swelling or chemical interaction.
- It's best when **only one diffusion mechanism** dominates.

Diffusion Responses of CFRP (Vinyl Ester) Specimens

- **Dual-Stage (Non-Fickian) Diffusion Model:**

$$M(t) = M_{\infty} \cdot (1 - [A \cdot e^{-k_1 t} + (1 - A) \cdot e^{-k_2 t}])$$

- M_t : Moisture uptake at time t
- M_{∞} : Final Saturation % weight gain)
- A: Weighting coefficient (fraction of fast process, 0-1)
- K1: Rate constant for fast diffusion (1/day)
- K2: Rate constant for slow diffusion (1/day)
- **Interpretation:**
 This model captures **non-Fickian behavior**:
- Surface/interface water diffuses fast initially (via k1),
- Then slows due to matrix effects or saturation (via k2).
- It's commonly used in **composites**, where **resin-matrix interaction** or **microstructure** delays uniform diffusion.

Conclusions

- **Mechanical Performance**

- Significant mechanical property loss across all modes of **Onyx** especially in **compression (–65%)** and **tensile modulus (–56%)**.
- **Vinyl Ester** degraded in all metrics.
- **Epoxy** showed increased stiffness (+21%) but reduced ductility (–7.5% strain).
- **Onyx** exhibited strength loss.

- **Microstructural Observations**

- **Profilometry**: Surface roughness and crack growth increased over time.
- **Micro-CT**: Water pockets, salt ingress, and fiber–matrix debonding (notably in Epoxy).
- **SEM**: Clear signs of **salt crystallization, matrix cracking, and water pockets**.

- **Saline exposure leads to brittleness, interfacial damage, and mechanical degradation.**
- **Protective design and material choices are essential for marine durability.**

Future Work

- Longer-term degradation studies.
- Testing in more varied and extreme marine conditions.
- Optimization of 3D printing parameters.
- Developing predictive models for degradation.

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Thank you!

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